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REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Druskininkai – Lithuania

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1. Introduction

The main aim of this report was to collect information regarding the situation of rural areas and the communities residing in each of the participating regions in the ESIRA project (ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS HORIZON 101136253). These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

This report aimed to go beyond the literature and statistical data available and, together with the organisations participating in the pilots, explore the regions' situations and the drivers behind the disadvantages.

The report introduces the territorial organization of Lithuania and analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, focusing on territorial inequalities.

A deeper examination of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts was done in Druskininkai municipality. The municipality represents the typical rural region and demonstrates the major challenges to rural people. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the municipality were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of the leading local social economy stakeholders.

2. Methodology

The research method combines and integrates qualitative and quantitative research methods in a single research study. It involves collecting and analyzing qualitative and quantitative data to understand a phenomenon better and answer the research questions.

The research questions are grouped into 5 main topics:

1. Overview of the country's territorial system and main information about social exclusion and inequalities; and main existing national policies to support local development and social inclusion and social economy in rural areas,
2. Information about the region presented in the report and main existing local policies, services and initiatives to support social inclusion and social economy in rural areas,
3. Social exclusion, inequality in the region, (social) economy in the region,
4. Main challenges and assets in the region,
5. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP.

The information was collected via literature reviews, including regional, local, and national strategies and statistics, complemented by expert interviews with policymakers, administration, or service providers, and organisations representing stakeholders and vulnerable groups.

MAP of Druskinkai municipality was established in 2024 by project partners and local stakeholders of the social economy. The stakeholders were the following:

- local policymakers from the Municipality of Druskininkai,
- heads or experts of regional institutions providing social and employment services,
- representatives of local businesses, including SMEs and social enterprises,
- representatives of local civil society organisations.

First MAP meeting was organised in March 2024. Meeting participants represented the science, policy, business, and society sectors. In the first part of the meeting, the project was introduced, and the roles of the meeting participants and the aim of the MAP were discussed. In the second part of the meeting, the Focus group was organised. The main aim of the discussion was to identify the main actors of marginalised groups and the main drivers of social exclusion in the Druskininkai region. In the last part of the meeting, all participants filled out a questionnaire (see Annex 1). In total, we have received 18 filled questionnaires. Respondents are listed in Annex 2.

3. Country overview: Lithuania

3.1 Territorial system of the country

The territorial administrative units of the Republic of Lithuania are counties and municipalities. The territory of the Republic of Lithuania currently comprises 10 counties and 60 municipalities. The county is a higher administrative unit. It is formed from the territories of the municipalities characterized by common social, economic and ethno-cultural interests. The territorial administrative units of the Republic of Lithuania consist of residential areas, which are divided into urban and rural residential areas. Cities and towns are attributed to urban, townships, villages and isolated farmsteads – to rural residential areas (Official Statistics Portal, 2024). Lower administrative units of municipalities are elderates.

Until 2010, the counties were administered by county governors appointed by the Government of the Republic of Lithuania. Their main duty was to ensure that the municipalities obey the laws and the Constitution of Lithuania. Ongoing discussions about administration units of Lithuania in the Government and in the Parliament in Lithuania in 2009-2010 have finished with a conclusion that 10 counties are too small units for Lithuania for governing purposes as the two smallest counties have administered only four municipalities. Therefore, on 10 March 2010, the administrations of counties were liquidated by the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Lithuania, but the counties themselves have retained for statistical and reporting purposes (Resolution on the Liquidation, 2010).

Figure 1. Counties and municipalities of Lithuania.

Source: Wikipedia, 2024.

Based on the European Commission delegated regulation (EU) 2023/674 of 26 December 2022 amending the Annexes to Regulation (EC) No 1059/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council

on the establishment of a common classification of territorial units for statistics (NUTS), the following classification of Territorial Units for Statistics are in Lithuania:

- NUTS level 1 corresponds to country – Lithuania (NUTS1: country (LT0)).
- NUTS level 2 corresponds to the Capital Region and Central and Western Lithuania Region (NUTS2: regions - Capital Region (LT01) and Central and Western Lithuania Region (LT02)).
- NUTS level 3 corresponds to counties – 10 counties in Lithuania (NUTS3: counties – Vilnius county (LT011), Alytus county (LT021), Kaunas county (LT022), Klaipėda county (LT023), Marijampolė county (LT024), Panevėžys county (LT025), Šiauliai county (LT026), Tauragė county (LT027), Telšiai county (LT028), Utena county (LT029) (Official Statistics Portal, 2024).

To meet the demand for statistics at a local level, Eurostat maintains a system of local administrative units (LAUs) compatible with NUTS. These LAUs are the building blocks of the NUTS, and comprise the municipalities and communes of the European Union (Eurostat, 2024).

Based on validated of LAU 2022 list, in Lithuania there are 60 municipalities (LAU level), with max population of 563,012 inhabitants, with min. population of 3,903 inhabitants; average population 46,767 inhabitants; total amount of inhabitants 2,805,998 (Eurostat, 2024).

Elderships are the smallest administrative territorial units in Lithuania since in 1994 when a Law on Local Self-Government was implemented (Law on Local, 1994). There was a total of 555 elderships in Lithuania in 2023 (Official Statistics Portal, 2024).

3.2 Strategies and policies

The main policies to support local development in rural areas are Lithuania's recovery and resilience plan, CAP Strategic Plan of Lithuania 2024–2027, and Community-led Local development strategies.

Lithuania's recovery and resilience plan. Lithuania has prepared its Recovery and resilience plan under the EU Commission call for the REPowerEU Plan in response to the energy market disruption caused by Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Under REPowerEU, EU countries are updating their recovery and resilience plans with new measures to save energy and diversify the EU's energy supplies. Recovery and resilience plan of Lithuania has responded to the urgent need to foster a strong recovery, while making Lithuania's economy and society more resilient and future-ready. The reforms and investments in Lithuania's plan, approved by the Council on 28 July 2021, are helping it to become more sustainable, resilient and better prepared for the challenges and opportunities of the green and digital transitions. Following Council approval of Lithuania's plan on 28 July 2021, Lithuania's updated recovery and resilience plan, including a REPowerEU chapter, was approved on 9 November 2023. The transformative impact of Lithuania's plan is the result of a strong combination of reforms and investments which address the specific challenges of the country. The reforms address bottlenecks to lasting and sustainable growth, while investments are targeted to address common European challenges by embracing the green and digital transitions, to strengthen economic and social resilience and the cohesion of the Single Market. In particular, Lithuania's plan will accelerate reforms and

investments in education as well as healthcare. The plan will also invest in more sustainable power generation and energy storage, promote green mobility, facilitate the 5G rollout and strengthen social protection (European Commission, 2024).

Local development in this plan is included in the chapter “Economic and social resilience”. Key macro-economic challenges for the Lithuanian economy include the need to improve tax compliance and broaden the tax base to sources less detrimental to growth and the need to address income inequality, poverty and social exclusion, including by improving the design of the tax and benefit system. Furthermore, the quality and efficiency of education and training, including adult learning as well as the quality, affordability and efficiency of the healthcare system needs to be further improved. The focus on investment-related economic policy on innovation should be stronger and productivity growth should be stimulated by improving the efficiency of public investment (European Commission, 2024).

Key measures in reinforcing economic and social resilience

The plan reinforces economic and social resilience with reforms and investments aimed at improving the resilience, quality, affordability of the healthcare system. Measures will focus on modernising the infrastructure of healthcare facilities, developing five centres of expertise in infectious diseases, and investing in the digitalisation of the health system (€268 million).

The plan includes measures to ensure high quality accessible lifelong education through consolidating teaching and learning resources, improving preschool, primary and secondary education, vocational education and training (VET) and adult learning (€312 million).

It also supports higher education and support for innovation by changing the funding model of the higher education system and making research and innovation support policies more efficient by consolidating existing agencies (€200 million).

In its plan, Lithuania also focuses on stronger social protection by reforming a guaranteed minimum income protection scheme, increasing coverage of unemployment social insurance as well as investing in a more customer-oriented employment, training and entrepreneurship support focusing on the twin transition (€109 million).

The plan includes reforms and investments in increasing the efficiency of the public sector, namely improvements in tax compliance and broadening the tax base, enhancing the budgetary framework, and improving human resources management in the public sector (€63 million).

Source: The European Commission, 2024.

“Millennium School Progress Programme” is part of the Recovery and resilience plan of Lithuania. The objective of the program is to reorganize and improve school infrastructure and ensure equal access to education for Lithuanian children, regardless of where they live, and socio-economic background. This is particularly important for rural areas, where the number of children is decreasing, and local schools are progressively closing.

CAP Strategic Plan of Lithuania 2024–2027. The plan aims to promote the sustainable development of the country's agriculture and food sector. This will be achieved by increasing the added value and the competitiveness of the sector, supporting farm viability (especially of small- and medium-sized farms), promoting sustainable production methods, while also ensuring adaptation to climate change and nature conservation. Enhancing innovation and increasing the attractiveness of rural areas are also emphasised (Lithuania's CAP strategic plan, 2023).

The Plan puts a strong emphasis on ensuring a fair income for farmers. A total of around EUR 3 billion is allocated for income support (covering approximately 2.8 million hectares) and will contribute to maintaining local production. Particular attention in the Plan is also paid to ensuring a fairer distribution of income support among farmers by allocating 20% of the above amount to small- and medium-sized farms to improve their viability. Additional support is given to sectors in difficulty to help address the challenges they face and improve the quality, competitiveness or sustainability of their output. An important share of the CAP support, around 35% of rural development funding, is allocated to farm modernisation (including farms of young farmers) and sustainable investments, such as investments in modern machinery for more sustainable fieldwork, more animal-friendly stables or renewable energy (Lithuania's CAP strategic plan, 2023).

Community-led local development will continue to play an important role and will be implemented with the LEADER approach, which brings together public, private and civil-society stakeholders to find shared solutions for the development of the rural economy and society. Stakeholders will come together in 49 local action groups, which will reach all rural areas in Lithuania; they will implement tailor-made local initiatives, in particular aimed at addressing the pressing challenges of employment and social exclusion in rural areas. These activities will, for example help in creating and developing services and businesses in rural areas, using local resources, markets and knowledge to support sustainable development (Lithuania's CAP strategic plan, 2023). In November 2023, 49 strategies of the LAGs were approved by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania and submitted to the National Paying Agency to organize calls under the intervention measure "Community-led local development (Leader)" of the Lithuanian Strategic Plan for Agriculture and Rural Development 2023-2027. In 2024 LAG's have started to invite stakeholders to prepare project proposals for implementation of the LAG strategies. **Community-led Local development strategies.** 49 community-led Local development strategies were submitted for the new programming period 2024–2027. The themes of the Local Development Strategies (LDSs) prepared by the Local Action Groups (LAGs) in the Strategic Plan for Lithuanian Agriculture and Rural Development 2023-2027 are diverse, focusing on the development of business and the search for solutions to social problems. The Strategic Plan continues to motivate community-driven rural development on the basis of a bottom-up approach, by funding local development strategies to address local challenges and needs with focus on social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas. Almost €74.9 million is available for the new period 2023–2027 (The Ministry of Agriculture, 2023). LAGs have included specific tools defined for social economy organizations in community-led Local development strategies, for example, 'Creating and developing NGO social business' is one out of 6 measures of Ignalina LAG strategy for 2023-2029 (Rural Development Strategy of Ignalina 2023-2029, 2023). Some

LAGs' have decided to give additional points for projects that focus on the inclusion of socially vulnerable groups, or if they develop services based on their needs.

Other strategies and policies for regional development in Lithuania. OECD in its Regional Outlook (2023) provides systematic information about policy regulation in Lithuania, defining objectives of regional policy, legal and institutional framework for regional policy, budget allocation to regional development, national regional development policy framework, etc. (OECD Regional Outlook 2023).

Table 1 Objectives, framework and budget allocation for regional policy in Lithuania

Key regional development challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different regional economic growth potential and uneven economic development, with some regions at risk of greater poverty and social exclusion - An insufficiently sustainable environment, which negatively affects the attractiveness of the regions
Objectives of regional policy (Law on Regional development, Nr. VIII-1889, 2000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote regional adaptation to changing economic and social conditions by exploiting and strengthening each region competitive advantage - Increase the infrastructure and service efficiency, ensuring their accessibility - Reduce social and economic disparities across and within the regions
Legal/institutional framework for regional policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Law on Regional Development (Nr. VIII-1889, 2000) - The Law on Strategic Management (Nr. XIII-3096, 2020) - The Strategic Management Methodology (Nr. 292, 2021)
Budget allocated to regional development	Budget of the Regional Development Programme for 2022-2030 and Programme for the EU funds' investments in 2021-2027 for the implementation of Regional Development Plans (€1,623.9 million of EU Structural Funds (ERDF, CF, ESF+) and €378.1 million of national co-financing.)
National development framework regional policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The National Progress Plan (NPP) identifies the main strategic goals and objectives to be achieved in all public policy areas. Strategic objective #7: Sustainable and balanced development of the territory of Lithuania and reduction of regional exclusion. The NPP constitutes the basis for the Regional Development Programme. - The Regional Development Programme for 2022–2030 (RDP) outlines the implementation directions of NPP strategic objectives, assigning responsibilities to Regional Development Councils and/or municipalities based on their competencies. - The 10 Regional Development Plans (RDPLs) are created by each region's Regional Development Council to identify social, economic, and environmental issues and their causes, set development goals and objectives, establish monitoring indicators, and plan progress measures with estimated funding.
Urban policy framework	Objectives of a national urban policy are integrated into the NPP and the RPP for 2022–2030
Rural policy framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objectives of a national rural policy are integrated into the NPP and the RPP for 2022–2030 - CAP Strategic Plan of Lithuania for 2023–2027
Major regional policy tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Structural Funds and national co-funding (27% of EUSF dedicated to Regional Development Programme for 2022–2030 and Regional Development Plans) - The Regional Development Programme for 2022–2030 (RDP) - The Regional Development Plans (RDPLs)
Policy co-ordination tools at national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Interior (national regional policy formation, organization, coordination and monitoring of its implementation) - National Regional Development Council (i.e., the collegial advisory body for the Government and the Ministry of Interior on national regional policy. It includes representatives from ministries, public authorities, the Association of Local Authorities in Lithuania, employers' and trade unions' organizations, the Council of Non-Governmental Organisations, the National Council of Community Organizations, and the chairs of Regional Development Councils)
Multi-level governance mechanisms between national and subnational levels	The National Regional Development Council is authorized to review and provide feedback on planning document projects approved by the Government, such as the Regional Development Programme, and regulations impacting regional development. It monitors the implementation progress of these documents and can propose improvements to the Government and Ministry of Interior. Additionally, it addresses other issues related to national regional policy formation and implementation.

Source: *OECD Regional Outlook 2023, 2023*.

Main instruments and programmes at national level to support local development in rural areas are the Lithuanian Rural Development programme 2024–2027 and the National aid – State aid implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania.

Lithuanian Rural Development programme 2023–2027. After a thorough examination and discussion of the proposals, the Council of the EU and the European Parliament adopted the CAP reform package in October 2020. Nine months later, a political agreement on all three CAP reform proposals was reached on 24–25 June 2021. The new CAP is more focused on environmental and climate objectives: 25% of direct payments will have to be dedicated to eco-schemes and 35% of rural development funds will have to be dedicated to environment and climate-related measures. A better targeting of support will be ensured, in particular for small and medium-sized family farms: redistribution of direct support will be compulsory and at least 10% of direct payments will have to be redistributed to small farms. At least 3% of the CAP budget will be allocated to young farmers. For the first time, the CAP will include social clauses, i.e. CAP support will only be granted to beneficiaries who comply with the requirements of European social and labour legislation. The new CAP implementation model will ensure that the focus is more on achieving the CAP objectives rather than simply complying with the rules, and will provide greater flexibility for Member States to tailor CAP interventions to their needs and specific local conditions. The new CAP has started in 2023 and will continue until the end of 2027 (Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

In total 6 measures and 9 actions of these measures from the Lithuanian Rural Development programme 2023–2027 are important to support local development in rural areas of Lithuanian regions aiming to use assets and potentials in the region and to decrease vulnerability and social exclusion. All these measures cover important elements for regional development: i) creation of good and needed infrastructure, ii) gathering of needed knowledge and skills, and iii) creation of good conditions for creation of businesses in rural regions. First two measures are related with new knowledge, information activities and advisory services: (1) Knowledge transfer and information activities; (2) Advisory services, farm management and farm relief services. Next measure focus on basic services and village renewal in rural areas supporting actions for (1) investment in all types of small-scale infrastructure; (2) broadband infrastructure; and (3) investments in rural cultural and natural heritage and landscape. Last two measures important for regional development are related with (1) farm and business development, and (2) establishment of producer groups and organisations. Actions for farm and business development focus on a) support for the establishment of young farmers; b) support for setting up in rural areas; c) support for small farms; and d) support for investments for setting up and developing non-agricultural activities.

National aid - State aid. State (hereinafter referred to as "national") support means State support for agriculture and rural development implemented under the Programmes for the Promotion of Agriculture, Food and Rural Development, Fisheries Development and Competitiveness, Phytosanitary, Plant Reproductive Material and Cereals Quality Control, and Varietal Research (hereinafter referred to as "Programmes"). The main objectives of the support are: (i) to increase the efficiency of farms

able to compete on Lithuanian and foreign markets; (ii) introduce promising production technologies; (iii) improve working conditions for farmers and rural population. The main source of funding for the Programmes is the State budget of the Republic of Lithuania. The Government of the Republic of Lithuania, in accordance with the allocation of State budget appropriations, approves each year the expenditure estimates for the Programmes by measure. The Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania shall accordingly approve the detailed estimates of the expenditure of the Programmes by measure. For each of the measures provided for in the Programmes, the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania or the competent authority shall approve the implementing rules, or amendments thereto, setting out the objectives and directions of the financing, the beneficiaries, the procedure for submitting documents and disbursing the aid, and the responsibilities (National Paying Agency, 2024).

In total two measures of National aid – State aid is important to support local development of rural regions in Lithuania: (1) Aid for the organisation of and participation in agricultural exhibitions, trade fairs and competitions; and (2) Aid for knowledge transfer and information activities. Local producers need support to get more information about product marketing, technologies, cooperation. Also, they need support to participate in exhibitions, fairs, etc.

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Lithuania

Various organizations within and outside Lithuania analyse territorial inequalities of Lithuania, e.g., the Regional Outlook of Lithuania and the Regions and Cities at a Glance initiated by OECD; Territorial patterns and relations in Lithuania initiated by ESPON¹; White Paper of Lithuanian Regional Policy for harmonious and sustainable development initiated by the Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Lithuania, assessment and classification of the Lithuanian regions in groups based on selected criteria as economic dynamism, rurality, periphery, aiming to group them in to urban, semi-rural or rural regions, etc. (OECD Regional Outlook, 2023; OECD Regions and Cities at a Glance, 2022; Lithuanian Regional Policy (White paper), 2017; Gedminaitė-Raudonė, 2011; Vidickienė, Gedminaitė-Raudonė, 2011; Gedminaitė-Raudonė, 2014; Pociūtė-Sereikiene, 2019; Pociūtė-Sereikiene et al., 2019, EPSON, 2021).

Classification of Lithuanian regions into groups as advantaged or disadvantaged regions depends on the needs of assessment, policy regulation, etc. Various criteria and indicators are used for this assessment, e.g., rurality, level of infrastructure, unemployment level, amount of investments, migration flows, etc. Summarising the above-mentioned resources, it can be concluded that **remote and peripheral regions, close to the borders, may be regarded as disadvantaged regions** in Lithuania.

The OECD Regional Outlook (2023) analyses recent trends, policy developments, and future prospects across OECD regions, highlighting the root causes of regional inequalities in performance and well-

¹ ESPON is an EU funded programme that bridges research with policies. Organization provides territorial analyses, data and maps to support EU development policies, and particularly Cohesion Policy, with facts and evidence. This organization also helps public authorities to benchmark their region or city, identify new challenges and potentials and shape successful development policies for the future.

being. The report offers evidence, guidance and policy recommendations to enhance competitiveness and productivity, promote inclusive growth, accelerate the net-zero transition and raise well-being standards through effective regional development policy and multi-level governance. Future orientations of regional policy proposed by the OECD focus on the following issues:

- Reducing interregional social and economic disparities by strengthening the most vulnerable areas, particularly in relation to target groups, public services, transportation, and environmental concerns.
- Mitigating intraregional social and economic disparities by implementing measures that address economic, social, or environmental issues specific to each territory.

Assessment of well-being of regions in Lithuania by OECD have proved that Lithuania has **large regional disparities** in 6 out of 11 well-being dimensions² with the largest disparities in the dimensions of jobs and community (OECD Regions and Cities at a Glance, 2022).

ESPON research on territorial patterns and relationship in Lithuania highlights that a fairly significant proportion of the population is at risk of poverty or social exclusion (2017). This is especially true for households outside the Vilnius region, where the level of risk ranges from 30% to 40%, compared to 20-25% in the Vilnius region. The population groups at particular risk are people who fall into one or more of the following categories: the unemployed, pensioners, people with disabilities, large families with three or more children, single parents and single people (EPSON, 2021).

Figure 2. People at risk of poverty and social exclusion in Lithuania in 2017

Source: ESPON, 2021.

² OECD well-being dimensions: (1) Jobs, (2) Community, (3) Life Satisfaction, (4) Education, (5) Housing, (6) Income, (7) Environment, (8) Access to services, (9) Civic Engagement, (10) Safety, (11) Health.)

Five external factors are identified in the White Paper of Lithuanian Regional Policy that will determine the long-term trends of the regions of Lithuania:

1. **globalisation** creates opportunities for developing exports and attracting investment, but it also requires an increase in the competitiveness of the country and its regions,
2. the **fourth industrial revolution** creates opportunities for increasing productivity, but threatens a decline in employment in traditional industries and requires more qualified workers,
3. **freedom of movement** within the EU creates opportunities for young people to acquire additional knowledge and skills, but it also requires improvement of the quality of education in the country so that it can compete with the best European schools and efforts to eliminate educational imbalances and to create conditions for those who intend to return to Lithuania to work once they complete their studies,
4. the prospect of **further EU development** raises questions about the size and structure of the EU budget as well as investment policy tools,
5. the changing **migration trends** and the geopolitical situation of the region allow Lithuania to become an immigration destination country (Lithuanian Regional Policy (White paper), 2017).

In the White paper, concrete actions are identified on how to improve conditions in the disadvantaged regions.

Assessment of the Lithuanian regions is also reflected in various research papers where regions are assessed based on selected criteria such as economic dynamism, rurality, periphery, etc.

Gedminaitė-Raudonė (2014) argues that new focus on the specific features of the regions and its competitiveness encourages using the regional policy measures reflective of broader conception of the rural countryside. The new target and monitoring oriented rural policy need typologies taking into account the diversity of rural regions. While creating region typologies for policy goals, it was essential to find new criteria and indicators for the measurement of the rural region's economic potential. The **economic dynamism** becomes an important indicator of the region's economic potential proposed by OECD organisation (Gedminaitė-Raudonė, 2011).

Pociūtė-Sereikiene et al. (2019) in their research analyse peripheral regions in Lithuania using peripheral region determination model, which combines location, demographic, social, economic, cultural, political and natural factors. By analysing the case of Lithuania using 1992–2012 data at the LAU-1 region level, the study revealed a polarized picture of the country and highlighted the factors influencing peripherality in different Lithuanian regions (Pociūtė-Sereikiene, 2019). The authors of the paper conclude that the highest peripherality level was seen in **the Southern and Northeastern regions** of Lithuania. These regions suffer from intensive depopulation, as well as rather low economic and social potential. At the same time, these are the most naturally intact regions in Lithuania (covered with forests and lakes). The Northern–Central–Western region shows medium peripherality. The calculations showed that weak economic potential is the dominant factor in the region. A large part of

this region suffers from depopulation as well as a decline of economic and social capacity. Conversely, the Central–Eastern region, which occupies a significant part of the Lithuanian territory, is distinguished by the lowest degree of peripherality and has the closest values to the country’s average. The Northwestern and Southwestern regions show contrastive peripherality. The peripherality of the Northwestern region is influenced by economic, political, demographic and social factors. The Southwestern region’s peripherality is also influenced by a group of factors; however, economic factors are dominant (Pociute-Sereikiene, 2019).

In 2021, the European Commission approved the Regional Aid Map for Lithuania, designating most regions as eligible for various EU support programs and measures. Europe has always been characterised by significant regional disparities in terms of economic well-being, income and unemployment. Regional aid aims to support economic development in disadvantaged areas of Europe, while ensuring a level playing field between Member States. In November of the same year, the European Commission has also approved the Lithuania's map for granting regional aid from 1 January 2022 to 31 December 2027 under EU State aid rules. The revised Regional Aid Guidelines (RAG), adopted by the Commission on 19 April 2021 and entering into force on 1 January 2022, enable Member States to support the least favoured European regions in catching up and to reduce disparities in terms of economic well-being, income and unemployment – cohesion objectives that are at the heart of the Union. They also provide increased possibilities for Member States to support regions facing transition or structural challenges such as depopulation, to contribute fully to the green and digital transitions. At the same time, the revised RAG maintained strong safeguards to prevent Member States from using public money to trigger the relocation of jobs from one EU Member State to another, which is essential for fair competition in the Single Market (European Commission, 2021).

Lithuania's Regional aid map specifies the Lithuanian regions eligible for regional investment aid and sets the maximum aid intensity, i.e., the maximum amount of State aid that can be granted per beneficiary, expressed as a percentage of eligible investment costs, for those areas. Under the revised RAG, the following regions of Lithuania will be eligible for regional investment aid:

- The region of **Central and Western Lithuania Region (LT02)** (in LT: *Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos regionas*) is among the most disadvantaged regions in the EU, with a GDP per capita below 75% of EU average. These regions are eligible for aid under Article 107(3)(a) TFEU (so-called ‘a’ areas), with maximum aid intensities for large enterprises between 30% and 50%, depending on the GDP per capita of the respective ‘a’ area. The region of Vidurio ir vakarų Lietuvos (with the exception of the county of Klaipėdos) will be eligible for an increase of the maximum aid intensity from 40% (on the basis of the GDP per capita) to 50%, due to the relatively high population loss experienced in these areas over the past decade.
- The region of Capital (in LT: *Sostinės regionas*) no longer qualifies as ‘a’ area in view of its positive economic development, but is now considered as a pre-defined region under Article 107(3)(c) TFEU (so-called ‘c’ area), as with all regions that qualified as ‘a’ areas in the period until 2021, and no longer qualify as such in the upcoming period. The maximum aid intensities for large enterprises in this area will be 35% (increased from 15%), as it borders the counties

of Alytaus, Kauno and Utenos, which are 'a' areas with a maximum aid intensity of 50% (The European Commission, 2021).

3.4 Social economy

3.4.1 The history of social economy in Lithuania

The roots of the social economy in Lithuania have started in the beginning of the 20th century by the emergence of cooperatives that developed organically from local communities. This grassroots movement laid the foundation for cooperative principles that later have influenced social enterprises in Lithuania. Cooperatives in Lithuania began to form in the early 20th century, driven by local needs for mutual aid and economic support among farmers and artisans. The social security system prior to World War II resembled the Bismarckian model, which emphasized social insurance but excluded many, particularly farmers, from benefits (Aidukaite, 2009). The cooperatives were characterized by democratic governance and profit-sharing, fostering a sense of community and collective responsibility (Civinskas et al., 2023). These cooperatives provided a buffer against economic hardships, allowing members to pool resources and share risks, which was crucial in the context of Lithuania's socio-economic landscape (Ramanauskas et al., 2017). The subsequent incorporation into the Soviet Union stifled cooperative growth, imposing a centralized economic model that undermined local initiatives (Aidukaite, 2009). After regaining independence in 1990, Lithuania faced challenges in reviving the cooperative movement, as the legacy of the Soviet system created barriers to understanding and implementing cooperative principles (Vilkė, 2016).

Until Lithuania regained independence in 1990, all state policy was based on centralised management. After 1990, the efforts were made to move from a centralised to a market-oriented economy and the 'welfare state' model was launched in order to improve the country's economic and social situation (Paluckiene, 1999). It was an ongoing discussion, that insufficient effort was put into the choice of a 'welfare policy' model, with a focus on economic indicators mostly and insufficient attention to the social security, welfare network and infrastructure development as well as the increase of the redistribution amounts, establishment of the workplaces and social security infrastructure, where existing problems were not observed enough (Maniokas, 2005). The aim was to improve economic situation, indicators and related policies as much as possible, but people were not involved in these reforms, even though they were considered as the subject of economic reforms (Rakauskienė, 2006, Varaškaitė, 2016).

Until now, the welfare model of Lithuanian social policy is oriented towards the liberal welfare model, with a focus on market factors, but it is worth emphasising that due to the inconsistent policy implementation in Lithuania's social policy, the features of all three models of the welfare state can be found as identified by Esping-Andersen (Vaidelytė, 2007, Varaškaitė, 2016). Since Lithuania's independence, the country's social policy has been oriented towards the conservative/corporatist welfare state model, which was based on the principle of social insurance, and the number of persons eligible to receive social insurance has been expanding throughout the period since independence in 1990 (Guogis, Bernotas, Ūselis, 2000). In this model, the role of non-investor owned enterprises

(typically, cooperatives) has been underestimated. However, features of the liberal welfare state model can also be observed in Lithuanian social policy, especially since Lithuania's accession to the European Union in 2004. The shift from a conservative/corporatist welfare state model to a liberal welfare state model in Lithuania has been significantly influenced by neoliberal policies and globalization. This transition has led to profound changes in social security and welfare provisions, impacting the socio-economic landscape of the country. Initially, Lithuania's welfare state was characterized by conservative and corporatist elements, focusing on social insurance and collective responsibility. The transition to a liberal model began post-2008 financial crisis, driven by neoliberal reforms that emphasized market solutions and individual responsibility (Atas, 2018). The liberal model has led to a rise in income inequality, as social safety nets have been weakened, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations (Atas, 2018). The shift has undermined traditional intergenerational solidarity, with a growing emphasis on means-tested benefits rather than universal entitlements (Ferge, 1997). Influences from supranational organizations like the World Bank have accelerated these changes, prioritizing economic efficiency over social welfare (Aidukaite, 2014). While the liberal welfare state model aims to foster individual empowerment and economic growth, it has also raised concerns about social cohesion and the adequacy of support for those in need. Critics argue that the rapid withdrawal of state support may lead to increased social unrest and dissatisfaction among the populace (Avlijas, 2020).

Social policy in Lithuania is characterised by an orientation towards the poorest segments of the population, but the protection provided by the state is very minimal and target oriented. The social protection system is aiming to involve more private organisations, and thus Lithuania's social policy model is becoming more and more similar to the liberal welfare state model (Bernotas, Guogis, 2006).

In recent decades, poverty and social exclusion, rising income inequality, an ageing population due to emigration, low birth rates and increasing life expectancy have been the main challenges facing social policy. The history of the social economy in Lithuania reflects a gradual evolution influenced by socio-economic changes and legislative developments. Initially, social enterprises existed in a limited capacity during the Soviet era, primarily focused on employing disabled individuals. However, the modern framework began to take shape post-independence, particularly with the enactment of the Law on Social Enterprises in 2004, which facilitated the establishment of over 100 social enterprises by 2020 (Moskvina, 2013). This transition highlights the growing recognition of social enterprises as vital components of the economy, aimed at addressing social exclusion and enhancing community vitality.

3.4.2 The most widespread types of social economy organizations in Lithuania

Social economy organizations can take a variety of legal forms:

- *Cooperatives* they are defined by their commitment to social and economic objectives that prioritize community welfare over profit maximization. These organizations operate under principles of solidarity, democratic governance, and member participation, making them vital in addressing social issues, especially for marginalized groups (Bouchard&Benoit, 2023).

- *Associations*, they are defined as self-governing entities formed voluntarily by individuals to serve community interests rather than for profit. These organizations embody principles of social solidarity and are integral to the social economy, which emphasizes social and environmental goals alongside economic activities. The following sections elaborate on the characteristics and roles of associations within the social economy (OECD, 2023).
- *Mutual benefit societies*, they play a crucial role in fostering social and economic well-being. These organizations prioritize the needs of their members and the community over profit generation, embodying principles of solidarity and cooperation. Mutual benefit societies are characterized by their focus on providing mutual support, particularly in areas such as health and social services, thereby contributing to social innovation and welfare systems (Bouchard&Benoit, 2023).
- *Foundations*, they as social economy organizations represent a critical intersection of economic and social objectives, focusing on the provision of essential goods and services that enhance community well-being. These organizations, prioritize social and environmental goals over profit, thereby fostering social innovation and resilience in local economies (Bouchard&Benoit, 2023).
- *Public enterprises*, they as social economy organizations play a crucial role in addressing societal challenges while balancing economic viability. These entities operate within a framework that prioritizes social objectives alongside financial sustainability, often filling gaps left by traditional market and state actors (Gertner, 2023).
- *Limited liability companies*, particularly the Low-Profit Limited Liability Company (L3C), serve as innovative structures within the social economy, blending profit motives with social missions. L3Cs are designed to attract funding for social enterprises while allowing for profit generation, thus bridging the gap between traditional for-profit and nonprofit organizations. This hybrid model enables social entrepreneurs to pursue charitable objectives using market-based strategies, thereby enhancing their financial sustainability and social impact (Artz&Sutherland, 2010).
- *Others*.

Community business in Lithuanian is broadly understood as a community initiative-driven business, where economic activities are carried out based on societal needs, and the profits are allocated to community activities to ensure that the community can meet its needs and solve its problems. There is no difference, where the community business is established and organizes its activity – in rural areas, or the city. Community business is considered a form of social business that focuses on meeting the public needs of the local community and solving social problems that affect the community. The community business concept arrives from the Lithuanian social business concept, which has been approved in by the Ministry of Economy of the republic of Lithuania in 2015 (Lithuanian Social Business Concept, 2015). From this point of view, the community businesses serve for developing harmonious interrelations within the community (integrates young and elderly, men and women, those living in

remote areas and partly excluded from daily community activity, etc.), and this adds to solving the issues of social exclusion and social economy.

3.4.3 How the social economy contributes to (local) development?

Poverty and social exclusion, rising income inequality, an ageing population caused by emigration, low birth rates and increasing life expectancy have been major social policy challenges in recent decades. Various support measures indicated in Law on Social Services, Law on Social Enterprises of the Republic of Lithuania and other legal acts contribute to local development aiming to reduce income inequality, improving the well-being of vulnerable groups, making the labour market more inclusive, improving the family environment, improving the well-being of people with disabilities, and strengthening social participation and community spirit (Law on Social Services, 2006; Law on Social Enterprises, 2004; Ministry of Social Security and Labour of the Republic of Lithuania, 2024; Ministerial Decree on the approval of the concept of social business, 2015).

3.5 Social enterprises in Lithuania

3.5.1 The history of social enterprises in Lithuania

Social enterprises in Lithuania have evolved significantly through three distinct historical stages: the pre-war period, the Soviet era, and the post-Soviet era.

Pre-War Period (Before 1940). During this time, social services were primarily provided by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) with strong volunteer bases. These organizations, often rooted in religious or civic traditions, addressed various social needs with minimal state involvement (Norvila, 2007).

Soviet Period (1940-1990). In these 50 years of experience, social services were nationalized, and voluntary action was reframed as mandatory public work, eroding the culture of genuine civic engagement. This period suppressed NGO activities and created a negative perception of public activism, which has had lingering effects on modern volunteering and social enterprises (Kurapkaitienė & Sadauskas, 2013; Urmanavičienė et al., 2021).

Post-Soviet Period (1990-Present). When Lithuania have regained independence again in 1990, social and economic challenges such as unemployment, poverty, and social exclusion prompted grassroots initiatives to address community needs. The NGO sector rebounded under the pressures of a neoliberal economic framework. Legislative milestones included the Law on Social Enterprises (2004), which aimed to support work-integration social enterprises (WISEs) through subsidies and policy incentives. Amendments in 2011 and new regulations in 2019 sought to refine the criteria and expand the scope of social entrepreneurship to include broader models like social business organizations (Law No. IX-2251, 2004; Law No. XIII-2427, 2019; Order No. 4-207, 2015). Many non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and cooperatives formed during this time can be seen as precursors to modern social enterprises, focusing on providing services to marginalized groups and fostering community development.

Legislative Framework of social enterprises in Lithuania. The year 2000 can be named as the beginning of formal recognition and support for social enterprises. In 2004, when Lithuania have joined the European Union, funding and policy alignment opportunities for social enterprises have started. The government adopted policies encouraging the development of social enterprises, particularly in addressing unemployment and integrating disadvantaged groups into the labour market.

The key legal framework for social enterprises in Lithuania is the Law on Social Enterprise and conception of Social Entrepreneurship:

- *Law on Social Enterprises (2004, No. IX-2251, amended in 2011):* This law formalized the status of WISEs, focusing on integrating vulnerable groups, including individuals with disabilities, into the workforce. WISEs were required to allocate at least 40% of employment to disadvantaged groups, with additional support for adapting workplaces (Urmanavičienė et al., 2021; Greblikaite et al., 2017). According to the Law, the main objective of social enterprises is to promote the reintegration into the labour market, social integration and the reduction of social exclusion of people who have lost their ability to work, are economically inactive and cannot compete on equal terms on the labour market, with the help of the State.
- *Conception of Social Entrepreneurship (2015):* This introduced broader definitions aligned with EU guidelines, aiming to reconcile the WISE-focused legal framework with emerging social business models (Order No. 4-533, 2016). The concept of social entrepreneurship expanded beyond work integration. Inspired by global trends and the growing availability of EU funds, Lithuanian social enterprises began diversifying their missions to include environmental sustainability, education, and community development.

The status of a social enterprise may be acquired by an enterprise (or its branch) established in Lithuania or in another country of the European Union, where the employees of these target groups (at least 4) account for at least 40 % of the annual average number of employees on the list, and which does not engage in economic activities included in the list of activities not to be supported by social enterprises, or where the income from such activities accounts for at most 20 % of the total income of the enterprise. The Law on Social Enterprises (2004, No. IX-2251) distinguishes two types of WISEs) of social enterprises on work integration:

- WISEs (a) in which at least 40% of employees are disadvantaged,
- WISEs for people with disabilities, which must represent at least 50% of the annual average number of employees. People with severe or moderate disability must represent at least 40% of employees, and the number of employees with disabilities must not be lower than 4.

The status of (work integration) social enterprises is mainly adopted by shareholder companies. Since 2004, associations can no longer acquire this status and public enterprises - since 2015 are not allowed to acquire this status (European Commission, 2024). The target groups to be employed firstly by social enterprises are: people with disabilities, long-term unemployed (with more than two years of unemployment since registration with the Employment Service under the Ministry of Social Security and Labour of the Republic of Lithuania), the unemployed over 50 years of age, also single parents

(adoptive parents), guardians or carers of a child who are bringing up a child (adoptive child) up to the age of eight or a disabled child (adoptive child) up to the age of 18, and other persons caring for a sick or disabled family member who is diagnosed as having a special need for permanent nursing care or special care/assistance, persons who have returned from imprisonment (where the period of imprisonment exceeded 6 months) and who have registered with the Employment Service no later than six months after the date of release, persons addicted to narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and other psychoactive substances, persons who have completed psychological, social and/or professional rehabilitation programmes (if the duration of their unemployment since their registration with the Employment Service exceeds 6 months).

Social business is characterised by a variety of business models: fee-for-service model, service subsidy model, employment model, cooperative model, organisational support model and others. A specific social business model demonstrates how social and economic value is created through the use of organisational structure, available social, economic and human resources, taking into account the components of the external environment, such as beneficiaries, clients and business partners. Social business can also apply some of the principles of several business models according to the nature of the activity, the target group or the objectives (Ministerial Decree on the approval of the concept of social business, 2015).

Since 2015 the term of social business is used in Lithuania. There are still many questions and debates about what social business is. Lithuanian Social Business Association defines social business is a kind of hybrid between an NGO and a business. It is an organisation that carries out a commercial activity and pursues a social or environmental mission. Social business is a business model that uses the market mechanism to link profit-making to social objectives and priorities, builds on socially responsible business and public-private partnerships, and embraces social innovation. Social business encompasses three main aspects: entrepreneurial (ongoing economic commercial activity), social (pursuit of social objectives) and governance (limited profit sharing, transparent management) (Lithuanian Social Business Association, 2024).

Social business can be carried out by for-profit companies whose economic activity is centred on social benefit, and by non-profit organisations whose business models are based on social value. Social business can take a variety of legal forms: *partnerships, companies, cooperatives, mutual insurance companies, associations, federations, foundations and others*. Social business is characterised by a variety of business models: fee-for-service model, service subsidy model, employment model, cooperative model, organisational support model and others. A specific social business model demonstrates how social and economic value is created through the use of organisational structure, available social, economic and human resources, taking into account the components of the external environment, such as beneficiaries, clients and business partners. Social business can also apply some of the principles of several business models according to the nature of the activity, the target group or the objectives (Ministerial Decree on the approval of the concept of social business, 2015). In 2017 the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania have adopted new decree on guidelines for the implementation of social business within the Rural Development Programme 2014-2020 programme

for the development of rural areas for the period 2014-2020” (No. 3D-720, November 2017). In the document definition of social enterprises and social innovation were provided with requirements for social enterprises to get the EU support. *A total of 7.474 social economy entities operates in Lithuania with employment of 68.573 people. The vast majority of them are public enterprises (4.845), followed by associations (1.951) (European Commission, 2024).*

The main sectors of activity:

- Cooperatives are mainly involved in the **agri-food (137), retail (88) and financial and insurance services (67)** sectors.
- Associations are mainly involved in the **creative, arts and entertainment sector (334)**.
- Foundations are mainly involved in the sector of the **human health activities (199)** (European Commission, 2024).

The most typical activities performed by social enterprises. The most typical activities performed by social enterprises are work integration in the following domains: cleaning, packaging, printing, sewing, furniture production and assembly, food production and processing (Universal Lithuanian Encyclopedia, 2024).

A national strategy/framework to support social enterprises. State aid for social enterprises is provided by the Employment Service under the Ministry of Social Security and Labour of the Republic of Lithuania: subsidies for the salaries of employees belonging to the target groups (50–75% of the salary, up to a maximum of two minimum monthly salaries, with an indefinite duration for the disabled and a maximum duration of two years for other target groups) and the national social security contributions calculated on the salaries, the costs of training these workers, the costs of setting up or adapting workplaces, facilities and the environment, production and recreation facilities for disabled people, additional administrative costs, transport costs and the costs of a sign language interpreter. Public procurement from social enterprises may be carried out in a simplified manner (to facilitate the sale of products), and they may be granted free of charge temporary possession and use of public and municipal premises on a loan basis (Universal Lithuanian Encyclopedia, 2024).

How social enterprises contribute to (local) development and to addressing the needs of vulnerable people? Social enterprises contribute to the local development by addressing the needs of vulnerable people in various forms: by employing them, inviting them to participate in the cooperation and co-creation activities, in activities organised by local communities. Many activities are organised by local communities by implementing projects approved by Local Action Group strategies. Associations of social enterprises and social business also contribute to local development and to addressing the needs of vulnerable people by the services they are providing. For example, Lithuanian Social Business Association provide the following services and also informs about other organizations that can provide necessary help:

- Resources for social business: guide for public services; Social Business Training platform; Social Business Facebook Group; Creative Shock Social Entrepreneurship Competition and Conference; Social Business Guide.
- Organizations supporting the development of social business: Versli Lietuva, Geri Norai, NGO Avily, [European Institute for Social Entrepreneurship Development and Innovative Studies](#), Lithuanian Junior Achievement.
- Acceleration programmes and incubators: [Changemakers'ON](#); [Enable Impact](#); [NGO Accelerator](#); [Altered State](#).
- Resources from abroad: [Ashoka Global SV Organisation](#); [SV courses PlusAcumen](#); [ChangemakersXchange Community of Social Entrepreneurs](#).

Good practice examples on social enterprises contribution to local development can be found in social media, various platforms of social business, etc.

One of the good practice examples is active social economy initiative in Druskininkai region - Viečiūnai community “Versmė”. Association “Versmė” is a part of Druskininkai LAG.

Viečiūnai community “Versmė” was established in 2003 and has a population of about 2000 inhabitants in the rural and border territory it represents. Association “Versmė” organises a children's day-care centre, social services for elderly lonely people, youth and various volunteering activities as well as environment improvement projects. Viečiūnai community implements various projects, which receive funding from the Druskininkai Municipality Rural Community Support Programme, the National Agriculture Ministry support programmes, LEADER programmes and many others. Association “Versmė” contributes to local development and social inclusion by tackling one broad social challenge – access to social services for people (children, youth, the elderly) in rural remote areas.

A favourable attitude towards community and social business is demonstrated by the local government, which has already included 2 rural communities in the network of social service providers and has made the inclusion of NGOs and community-based organisations in the network of social service providers one of its main goals.

4. Regional overview: Druskininkai region

4.1 Geographic and historical aspects

Druskininkai municipality is a municipality in Alytus county, southern part of Lithuania. In the north, the territory borders with 3 rural municipalities: Alytus, Lazdijai and Varėna. It is a border municipality with Belarus, and it is close to the border of Poland (50 km) as well. Druskininkai municipality consists of three inner units: Druskininkai city and two rural elderships: Leipalingis eldership and Viečiūnai eldership.

As much as 69% of the territory of the Druskininkai LAG consists of **forests**. Since ancient times, it has been customary for local residents to collect forest products - mushrooms and berries, and this is their additional source of income. Agricultural lands make up only a fifth of the total land fund. The land here is poor and not suitable for agricultural activities. The territory of Druskininkai LAG is **relatively sparsely populated**. In 2021, according to the population and housing census, the population density of the LAG territory was 16.7 inhabitants/km² and was significantly lower compared to the whole municipality of Druskininkai (44.3 inhabitants/km²), Alytus County (25.4 inhabitants/km²) and the country (43,1 inhabitant/km²) (Lithuanian Data Agency).

Historical aspects. The name of the city comes from the Lithuanian word 'druska', which means salt. Local sources are rich in minerals and their healing effects have been known for centuries. Druskininkai was named a health resort town as early as 1794, when the King of Poland decided to start developing tourism in the area. In the 18th century, Druskininkai appeared to be only an ordinary Lithuanian countryside site including 5 peasant homesteads. After the collapse of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth in 1795, Druskininkai devolved to the Czarist Russian Empire. Druskininkai, like many parts of Lithuania, has been occupied by Russians, Germans and Polish making national minorities significant to the area (Druskininkai History Information Center).

4.2 Demography

According to population and housing census data, in 2021 Druskininkai municipality had **19,016 residents**, 2,860 fewer than in 2011 (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy).

Figure 3. Number of residents in Druskininkai region.

Source: Statistics Lithuania; State Data Agency, 2024.

Comparing the population census data of 2011 and 2021, it is observed that the number of inhabitants in farmsteads, villages and towns with inhabitants between 201 and 1,000 is decreasing, but the population has significantly increased in towns with inhabitants between 1,001 and 2,999 inhabitants. For example, the total number of residents in the eldership centre Viečiūnai and Leipalingis has grown by 34% since 2011. Meanwhile, the number of inhabitants in villages and towns with between 201 and 1,000 inhabitants decreased by 47%, while the number of inhabitants in villages with up to 200 inhabitants remained similar and decreased by 4.7% (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency and Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy). In 2021, the population of Druskininkai municipality was composed of Lithuanians (91.6%), Polish (3%), Russians (2.2%), Belarusians (1%), Ukrainians (0.4%) and other nationalities (0.3%) (Lithuanian Data Agency). The total share of non-Lithuanian residents in Druskininkai municipality is **6.8%**. Following the start of the war in Ukraine in 2022, nearly 70,000 Ukrainians came to Lithuania. As a result, the Ukrainian population in the Druskininkai area increased to 803 by the end of 2022. During the first MAP meeting of ESIRA project, it was asked whether the Ukrainian people, and children especially, had any problems integrating into social life and education, and the MAP group reported that, thanks to the historical context and local residents' ability to speak Russian, Ukrainians successfully integrated not only on Druskininkai city but also in remote rural areas.

The median age of the population in Druskininkai municipality (46 years in 2014, 49 years in 2022) is higher than in Alytus County (48 years in 2022) or in the country (44 years in 2022), which shows that **the number of elderly residents in the municipality is increasing** (Lithuanian Data Agency).

The natural population change in the municipality of Druskininkai is negative – during 2014-2022 period, 1,400 more inhabitants died than were born in Druskininkai municipality (Lithuanian Data Agency).

From 2014 to 2021, the natural population change in Druskininkai municipality worsened compared to Alytus County and the national average. In 2014, the natural change rate per 1,000 residents was -6.4, declining to -12 by 2021. While Druskininkai's situation was better than Alytus County's, it exceeded the national average by 1.4 times in 2021 (Lithuanian Data Agency).

Figure 4. Natural population change per 1 thousand inhabitants.

Source: Statistics Lithuania; State Data Agency, 2024.

Net population migration in the territory of Druskininkai municipality has been negative since 2001. However, this indicator began to improve significantly from 2018, and from 2020 it became positive – as in 2020, 93 more people arrived in Druskininkai municipality, and in 2021 -34 more people than left (Lithuanian Data Agency). The reasons for this change are complex: continuous investments in high-quality living environment and services for residents, more attractive living environment, and finally, more flexible working conditions established after the coronavirus pandemic, allowing part of the population to work from any part of Lithuania.

Separately, it is worth noting that data for 2022 show a very significant increase in net migration in Druskininkai municipality. When evaluating the primary data of the Lithuanian Data Agency, a huge increase in the number of immigrants can be seen – it can be assumed that a part of this number consists of Ukrainians who came to Lithuania after the war in Ukraine started in 2022.

Economic situation. In 2021, the GDP per capita exceeded the national average in Vilnius and Kaunas counties and amounted to 148.8% and 102.1% respectively (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency). As in previous years, the gap in GDP per capita between Vilnius and other counties remains huge – in Vilnius County, this indicator exceeded the indicators of Alytus and other counties by more than two times.

Figure 5. GDP per capita, at current prices 2001-2021.

Source: Statistics Lithuania; State Data Agency, 2024.

The **average gross salary** in 2014-2022 was lower than the salary of both Alytus County and of Lithuania. At the end of 2022, this indicator in Druskininkai municipality was 2.8% lower than in Alytus County and 28.6% lower than the average of Lithuania (Lithuanian Data Agency). The lower wages than in the country can be explained by the fact that the Druskininkai municipality is dominated by the **tourism-oriented service sector**, in which the wages are lower than in financial, IT, etc. wages in the service or production sector.

During the period of 2014-2022, the **unemployment** rate in Druskininkai municipality decreased by 0.9%. and in 2022 it reached 10.7% which was higher than the regional (9.7%) and national indicators (9%) (see Fig. 2.1.6) (Lithuanian Data Agency). The share of unemployed women from the number of women of working age reached 9.5% and correlated with the national average. The share of unemployed men from the number of men of working age reached 12% and was 3.3% higher than the national average of the same indicator, which reached 8.7%. (Lithuanian Data Agency).

Figure 6. The percentage of the unemployed from the population of working age in 2014-2022.

Source: Statistics Lithuania; State Data Agency, 2024.

The trend that the share of unemployed men of working age in Druskininkai municipality is higher, compared to the average of the similar indicator nationwide, has been observed for a long time. High

unemployment and a higher proportion of unemployed men than men of working age are caused by the **lack of business enterprises**, especially in the construction and industrial sectors, and this can be explained by the specifics of Druskininkai municipality, as due to the geographical position of the city and its resort status, development of any industrial, warehousing and agricultural production and any polluting production is restricted (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy). Also during the first MAP (Multi-Actor Platform) meeting of ESIRA project it was noted that higher unemployment of working-age men is caused by three key issues: firstly, as a border region, it faces smuggling criminal activities and young men are one of the most vulnerable groups in this activity; secondly, as it was mentioned before, Druskininkai is famous for its seasonal fruit and mushrooms picking and therefore profitable seasonal works do not motivate to have long-term employment; thirdly, working-age men also is a group of people facing many social problems where alcoholism and long term unemployment are one of them (1st MAP meeting, 2024).

As a result, potential investors remain companies whose development directions are directly related to the development of tourism and recreation, medical services, green and clean industry. Meanwhile, Druskininkai municipality is not so attractive for investments for other economic entities (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029).

4.3 Institutional setting

Institutional setting such as access to services, education and health care is another important aspect of regions development. In Druskininkai municipality, there are **5 schools**. However, the number of general schools' pupils decreased dramatically over the last 20 years. For example, in Druskininkai municipality, this number decreased twice, while in Alytus County it decreased three times.

Figure 7. General school pupils (persons)

	2002-2003	2012-2013	2022-2023
Lithuania	594,313	373,874	344,337
Alytus county	32,059	18,910	14,220
Druskininkai municipality	4,663	2,521	2,233

Source: Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency, 2024.

Another important aspect of access to services is **proportion of preschool children to preschool education**. Over the past decade, preschool children in the Druskininkai area have faced worsening access to services compared to children in the Alytus region and the national average (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency).

Figure 8. Proportion of 1-6 years old children in preschool education, compared to the number of children of the respective age.

Source: Statistics Lithuania; State Data Agency, 2024.

Schoolchildren from Druskininkai municipality are more actively included to the informal education activities than the average of Lithuania. However, during the period of 2017-2022 (when such data is collected) this number decreased by 1%.

There are several institutions providing social services in Druskininkai. In the territory of the Druskininkai municipality, social services were provided by the non-stationary social services' budgetary institution, the Social Services Center of the Druskininkai municipality, and 21 non-governmental organizations: 5 public institutions (e.g. public organisation "Help the children" provides day care services for children and support for families in crises), 2 religious communities (Order of Malta and Archdiocese of Vilnius Caritas providing food and services for elderly), 10 associations (e.g., Society for the disabled people and the Pensioners' association organise leisure activities), 2 charity and support funds (charity organisation "Food bank" provides food for people with low income), and 2 rural communities (Viečiūnai town community "Versmė" and Leipalingis town community, both providing children's day care services) (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy).

The trend of **benefit recipients** over the last decade shows that the total number of people receiving social benefits has decreased significantly: in 2014, 1,020 people received benefits in the municipality of Druskininkai, while in 2022 social benefits were allocated to 591 residents (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency). An analogous trend of decreasing the number of persons receiving social benefits can be seen both in Alytus county and at the country level. However, it is important to note that the number of social benefit recipients, which decreased until 2020, increased again in 2021 and 2022 and returned to the level of 2019 (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency).

Healthcare is a significant issue in Druskininkai municipality, with the number of hospital beds per 10,000 residents decreasing dramatically since 2007. The situation is nearly twice as severe as the national average, making healthcare less accessible for older people or those who are in need. (Statistics Lithuania. State Data Agency).

Mobility and transport, accessibility. Druskininkai area is easily reachable via paved roads, which are mostly in good shape. Druskininkai area is crossed by the national roads Vilnius - Varėna - Grodno (No. A4, main road), Leipalingis - Kapčiamiestis (No. 2505), Leipalingis - Lazdijai - Kalvarija (No. 134), Druskininkai - Leipalingis - Seirijai (No. 180), Merkinė - Leipalingis (No. 133), regional roads Grūtas -

Druskininkai, Druskininkai - Marcinkonys, Druskininkai - Švendubre, local roads connect villages in the territory of the LAG (Google Maps, 2024).

According to the information directly provided by the Druskininkai municipal administration, the length of motor roads belonging to the Druskininkai municipality in 2022 was 432 km, of which 68 km in the city of Druskininkai and 364 km in the territory of the LAG (200 km in Leipalingis municipality, 163 km in Viečiūnai municipality). Most of the roads are paved with gravel – 217.4 km, earth – 109 km and asphalt concrete and cobblestone pavement – about 105 km. In Druskininkai municipality, 27% of local roads are unpaved, compared to 20% in Lithuania (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, 2024).

In the field of transport, projects have been implemented to increase the use of renewable resources, reduce pollution and noise.

In 2015, Druskininkai launched of a unique eco-friendly transport "Lynų kelias", the **cable car** in the very heart of the town (Lynų kelias, 2024). The electric-powered cable cars take people from the centre of Druskininkai to the "Snow Arena" (it is an artificial snow centre, with Druskininkai town viewpoint on the roof) in just a few minutes, avoiding the longer journey by car. This is a nature-friendly means of transportation as it does not pollute the environment and is superb entertainment for both children and adults.

Figure 9. Unique eco-friendly type of transport in Druskininkai "Lynų kelias".

Source: Lynų kelias, 2024.

According to the municipality administration's information, currently, there are nine **charging stations for electric cars** in the municipality. The charging network in the resort helps reduce noise and air pollution.

In the overall territory of Druskininkai municipality, **public transport** services are provided by the joint stock company "Kautra", and the renewal of the bus fleet has made the municipality's public transport 100% environmentally friendly (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, 2024). Accessibility to basic services for inhabitants of distanced areas is ensured by regularly scheduled bus transfers. The municipality provides transport to school and home for children. Smaller communities in villages organize informal self-support services and cooperate to meet the healthcare, shopping, or other needs for services or goods of elderly or lonely individuals residing in remote places. In the particular region, there exist **robust intergenerational connections**, with children assuming responsibility for meeting the needs for

goods and services of their parents or grandparents who live in remote rural areas of the municipality. So, the relatives provide the necessary support on demand.

4.4 Local policies and instruments

General outlines addressing the issues of social inclusion and social economy as well as social enterprises, in terms of policy measures, are defined in the main strategic document of Druskininkai region – ***Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029***. This is a long-term planning document designed to plan the general directions of environmental, social and economic development of a municipality. Druskininkai Strategic Plan is prepared in the context of other national planning documents at the strategic and programmatic level, as well as the municipality's spatial planning documents and the Regional Development Plan. It is highlighted in the document, that Druskininkai aims to significantly improve the quality of public services for its residents while ensuring the best services to visiting tourists who demand high-quality services. Until the year 2030, the focus will be on education, health and social services, culture and the creation and development of a competitive working environment, thereby restoring a balance between all the areas necessary for a harmonious life in Druskininkai. By stating the future vision, a hint is given to focus on the creation of favourable contextual conditions for social inclusion of a range of stakeholders, as well as the development of social economy: “Druskininkai of the future - a modern, contemporary, innovative, vibrant city that is attractive for not only for seniors and tourists but also for young families, and promising diverse aspiring young and ambitious professionals seeking a comfortable, quality and harmonious life in nature surrounded by a pleasant and harmonious environment.” (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029, p.14). Moreover, there is an indirect hint in the Strategic Development Plan, concerning the favourable conditions for social inclusion from its broadest perspective as accelerating power for social economy, because the area not only preserves community but also supports entrepreneurial and competitive decisions, creating new jobs and developing a progressive, green infrastructure. The combination of all these factors should inspire and empower the inhabitants of Druskininkai region to create a harmonious and fulfilling life and at the same time to attract visitors to come, discover, and return again and again.

More specifically, the Druskininkai Strategic Plan entails specific policy measures for supporting social economy, including social enterprises. The specific measure 1.1.3. “Empower and strengthen the youth community” focuses on enabling young people to meet the emotional, psychological and social needs of their families and physical health, develop youth initiatives and employment (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029, p.18). The specific measure 1.1.5. “Improve access to and quality of social security” refers to very explicitly defined actions to facilitate social economy in the region (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029, p.18-19). It is foreseen to increase the diversity and quality of social services, ensuring equal accession possibilities and non-discrimination by introducing 8 new social services, transferring at least 3 services to non-governmental organisations (social enterprises) and establishing 3 new infrastructure objects for providing social services. The increased access to social assistance and relevant information concerning these issues will be reached by establishing a helpline, improving the effectiveness of social assistance, and implemented citizen information campaign. Municipal and social housing will be expanded, and social housing will be proposed to 5 more families. Promotion of

employment for all, and competitive participation in the labour market is foreseen to be implemented via a targeted employment programme for people with disabilities. The specific measure 1.3.1. “Creating a business-friendly environment” next the aim of improving general conditions for business in the region, has a specific focus on community businesses by implementing at least 2 specific programmes to promote community entrepreneurship through year, and enabling diversification of existing tourism activities by adding alternative services, directed to contribute to social economy in the region (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029, p.20-21). And the last relevant measure is 2.2.2. “Enhancing community building and volunteering”, devoted to promoting progressive rural and urban communities and their environments, and strengthening the role of non-governmental organisations and promoting volunteering, especially in the areas related to the core needs of vulnerable groups in the region (Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029, p.23-24).

Targeted policy measures to support social inclusion and development of social economy in Druskininkai region rural areas are defined in the main document - *Local Development Strategy for Druskininkai Rural area for the years 2023-2027*, i.e. **Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy**, which was approved in 2023. Based on the Vision outlined in this strategy, the region is prioritizing the development of the rural area of Druskininkai harmoniously, employing the **collaborative community approach**. Until 2030, there are four main areas in the Vision, and two of them are directed to the issues of social inclusion and social economy/enterprises. First, it is stated in the Vision, that ensuring the availability of services that are important to residents and tourists will lead to a higher quality of life, increased attractiveness, and social inclusion. The evidence has been collected, that the overall population in the territory is growing; however, in some groups, tendencies are opposite (please see above, fig.8). The number of tourists in Druskininkai municipality is growing as well. So, there is a need to exploit the tourism potential of this territory, and it is vital to ensure that the needs of both residents and visitors are met and that they receive the services they need. Local residents proposed that priority be given to increasing access to social services and health care, and to developing tourism infrastructure and services. This can be done by collaborating with the growing NGO sector and strong local communities, and by drawing on the success of EU funding. Indeed, these measures relate to the objectives of the most important higher-level strategic documents for the region: 1) Druskininkai Municipality Strategic Development Plan 2021-2029; 2) European Union Funds Investment Programme 2021-2027; 3) Strategic Plan for Lithuanian Agriculture and Rural Development 2023-2027, and 4) National Progress Plan 2021-2030. However, no direct investment from this measure is foreseen in the Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p.41). And second, it is foreseen in the Vision, that people will be actively involved in local communities and develop social and community businesses. The evidence has been collected, that the tourism potential of the LAG territory - cultural heritage sites, amateur art, national heritage and crafts, traditional events, beautiful landscape - is under-utilized (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p.42). Local residents stated that the main shortfalls are in employment and leisure services, youth leisure employment and other services for young people. Therefore, it is necessary to stimulate the growing activity of communities and NGOs, to support initiatives aimed at exploiting the tourism potential, to promote the traditions and culture of the region, to promote events and to disseminate information about them in order to attract local

residents and resort guests and thus deal with social exclusion issues. This measure also relates to the objectives of the most important above-mentioned higher-level strategic documents for the region, however no direct investment from this measure is foreseen in the Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p.42).

Next to that, the indirect effect of collaborative community approach is defined in two more areas: the most valuable natural and cultural heritage objects of the Druskininkai region, if used in a smart way for the needs of local residents and tourists, will increase the attractiveness of the region and highlight its uniqueness, which will contribute to the economic well-being of local residents; and the agricultural sector will successfully introduce innovative technological solutions and share best practices (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p.47). The members of the LAG identified the purpose of their organisation, i.e. its mission - to become a success story of Druskininkai region, and directly address some important aspects of social inclusions and socially sensitive issues in its further explication: to contribute to the reduction of poverty, social exclusion and unemployment in the LAG area, and to involve young people in local community organization and to realize the potential for volunteering in the LAG area.

There are also pre-defined relevant general **Common Agricultural Policy** (CAP) measures, explicitly devoted to the issues of social inclusion and vulnerable groups (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 49, 51-52). The direct contribution is defined by distinguishing the strategic objective No. 8 (SO8): [SO8] Promoting employment, growth, gender equality, including women's participation in farming, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including circular bio-economy and sustainable forestry (SO8, p.49). The indirect contribution might be found in optional CAP strategic objectives objectives 3 and 7: [SO3] Improving the farmer's position in the value chain, and [SO7] Attracting young farmers and other new farmers, supporting their activities and facilitating sustainable business development in rural areas. Thus, Druskininkai rural LAG will contribute to the general EU CAP results in the field of economic growth and job creation in rural areas [R37], as aims to support the creation of 8 new job places until 2030 and will promote social inclusion [R42] by reaching the amount of 112 people benefiting from supported social inclusion projects (p. 52). (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 51-52).

Moreover, there are defined several specific measures concerning the issues of social inclusion and social economy/social enterprises. The specific Measure 3 “Creating and developing social business” aims to create at least 1 social business job place until 2029 and reach at least 3 services provided by social businesses for residents and/or visitors by the year 2029 (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 54). The predefined funding for this measure equals 70 thousand euros (p. 59). The specific Measure 6 “Promoting employment and integration of the population” aims to increase the integration of people experiencing social exclusion or at risk of social exclusion through participation in organized activities, reaching the integration of 12 persons, experiencing social exclusion or at social risk (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 56). The predefined funding for this measure is devoted to 4 projects, with the amount of 28 thousand euros in total (p. 59). The specific Measure 8 “Creating and developing community businesses” is tightly related to the social inclusions and social business, as Druskininkai rural residents consider the community business as a form of socially inclusive business. By the end in the year 2029,

it is expected to create at least 1 community business job place until 2029, and reach at least 3 services provided by community businesses for residents and/or visitors (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 56). The predefined funding for this measure is foreseen for 2 projects, with the amount of 240 thousand euros in total (p. 59).

Summing up, the Druskininkai rural LAG recognizes that the primary driving force for social inclusion and the development of social economy and social/community businesses in the rural areas of Druskininkai is an active involvement of rural communities, proactive leaders, forward-thinking farmers, and the younger generation, regardless of gender.

The most important *issue-specific initiative* is the **targeted social services provision activity**, performed by a municipal institution established for this purpose – Druskininkai Municipality Social services centre. The Centre implements number of different social services provision programs. The Centre provides and organizes preventive and general social services, accredited social care services, and integral assistance services for socially vulnerable groups in the area. Moreover, the Centre pays out the aid money and provides support with technical equipment on demand. It also organizes and co-ordinates complex services provided to the family, visits the person's (family's) home, determines the need for social services, and assesses the level of independence of a person who has reached the old-age retirement age in the process of determination of the person's special needs. Moreover, the Centre organizes and assists victims and perpetrators of violence, carries out prevention, organizes and provides assistance to third parties with addictions, and carries out prevention. The Centre maintains records of the support received and distributes the support, it also co-ordinates and organizes volunteer activities and co-operates with the administration of Druskininkai municipality, other state or municipal institutions and bodies, non-governmental organizations, communities, family members of a person and their relatives, following its competence while solving the issues of social inclusion and social assistance for vulnerable groups on demand. There are two permanent social economy organizations under the supervision of Druskininkai Municipality Social services centre, which provide social services to vulnerable groups in the region. To fight the childcare problems in Druskininkai region, the Care centre was established in 2018. The Care Centre aims to introduce and develop services that promote and support the care of children in a family environment, ensuring their needs and safety. The care centre is staffed by two care coordinators, 2 persons certified by the State Authority for the Protection of Children's Rights and a psychologist. There are 2 on-call foster carers in the care centre, with whom mutual cooperation and service provision agreements have been concluded. They are available at any time of the day to receive 5 children aged 0-17 years without parental care. Another social services provider is the Day care centre for people with disabilities. Day care centre for people with disabilities provides social services, concerning the provision of necessary information, counselling, mediation, advocacy and communication. It organises meals, feeds where necessary, develops and maintains skills for daily living and work, promotes self-expression and creativity, plans and organises activities and recreation. The staff of the Centre helps disabled people with personal hygiene and organises physiotherapy, occupational therapy, and physiotherapy sessions if necessary. Social services include communication with relatives to help them understand the needs of people with disabilities, etc.

Concerning the most important *issue-specific initiatives*, it should be highlighted, that on the 27th of February 2015, the Druskininkai LAG together with the Pagėgiai LAG set up the **public enterprise "Salty Winds"**. "Salty Winds" is a group of organisers of guided tours and programmes with many years of experience in working with artists, craftsmen and farmers providing services in the municipality of Druskininkai. This institution plays a very important role concerning the issues of social inclusion, but moreover – the development of social economy and social/community enterprises. The institution aims to provide opportunities for local residents, farmers, craftsmen, artists, rural communities of Druskininkai region to present their services and products more widely, thus strengthening their activities, their ideas and the collaborative spirit. Currently, "Salty Winds" works with more than 25 different natural and legal entities in the rural area, involving more than 110 local residents of Druskininkai. As for now, the "Salty Winds" aims to involve more socially vulnerable residents to contribute to social economy development in the region. As for now, collaboration with specifically social economy organizations is not of large extent, since such kinds of organizations are not widely spread as official entities in the region. Socially vulnerable groups in the region are jobless solely people, families and particular community members, who are in greater demand for involvement in economic activities to fight social exclusion because of economic, age, disability, loneliness and other socially sensitive issues. "Salty Winds" also cooperates with tourist facilities, spa centres and entertainment providers in Druskininkai to offer the widest range of services to tourists and local residents and thus to ensure the involvement of local people in economic activities, with help fighting the issues of social exclusion. The organization offers guided programs, entertainment, events, training and conferences, and other services, and promotes the products of local residents. "Salty Winds" is a successful public enterprise, providing services to 2000-3000 clients annually (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, p. 37), and this is an exemplary initiative how to foster social inclusion and social economy within the rural region.

To sum up, the regional overview revealed these **main social issues in Druskininkai area**:

1. The **decline of population** and especially in remote rural areas,
2. Older and **aging population**,
3. Negative **net migration** for many years, however recently positive net migration comes with possible immigration challenges to the area,
4. **GDP per capita** twice smaller than the average of Lithuania, lower salaries,
5. High **unemployment**, especially between men,
6. **Health care** issues and decline **access to services** for older and people in need.

At the same time, Druskininkai area had already stepped forward and institutionalized social issues-sensitive solutions in the most relevant region-specific planning documents and already establishes initiatives:

- general directions of environmental, social and economic development of a municipality are defined in long-term planning document - **Druskininkai Strategic Plan 2021-2029**,

- specific rural issues-sensitive long-term development foresight, concerning the questions of social inclusion and social economy/social enterprises, are outlined in another long-term planning document – **Local Development Strategy for Druskininkai Rural Area 2023-2027** (Druskininkai Rural LAG Strategy, 2023),
- targeted activities for social inclusion and support of vulnerable groups are organized via various social programs, implemented by a specific municipal institution established for this purpose – **Druskininkai Municipality Social Services Centre**,
- targeted activities for collaboration in fostering social economy and social/community enterprises are organized by the **public enterprise "Salty Winds"**, which aims to provide opportunities for local residents, farmers, craftsmen, artists, rural communities of Druskininkai region to present their services and products more widely, thus strengthening their activities, their ideas and the collaborative spirit.

5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Druskininkai region

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

According to data from the official statistics portal of Lithuania and regional studies in the field, over the past decade, the economic situation in Druskininkai municipality has been steadily improving, with the continued attraction of new investments, job creation, rising employment and incomes of the population, and a decline in the number of unemployed people and unemployment rate.

At the same time, the total number of people receiving social benefits has significantly decreased: in 2014, 1 020 people received social benefits in Druskininkai municipality, while in 2022, 591 people received social benefits. A similar downward trend in the number of people receiving social benefits can be seen in Alytus county and nationally. The share of long-term recipients of social benefits among all social benefit recipients was 21,2% in 2022. The comparison of the number of social benefit recipients per 1,000 inhabitants in Druskininkai municipality with Alytus county shows that the indicators do not differ substantially from 2018 (when such an indicator started to be tracked), but there is a significant gap with the national indicator, which is 1.3 times higher than in Druskininkai municipality, i.e., the situation in Druskininkai municipality is better than the average situation in the country. However, it is important to note that the number of recipients of social benefits, which had been declining until 2020, increased again in 2021 and 2022 and returned to the 2019 level. The increase in the number of social benefit recipients is mainly due to two global external factors that have created new challenges for the social assistance system: the COVID-19 pandemic that started in late 2019 and the war in Ukraine in early 2022.

Figure 10. Number of recipients of social assistance benefit per 1000 population.

Source: Statistics Lithuania, 2024.

The **Covid-19 pandemic** has dramatically changed the lives, relationships, patterns, and incomes of all segments of society, and increased the number of vulnerable people. Although the pandemic is over, a wide range of assistance is still needed, both short and long-term, for the elderly, the disabled, those who have lost their jobs and incomes, and single persons and families, especially those at social risk (Druskininkai Municipality Social Services Plan 2023, 2023).

Since the Russian Federation launched widespread military aggression on 24 February 2022 against **Ukraine**, war refugees have been arriving regularly in Lithuania. According to the Ministry of Social Security and Labour of the Republic of Lithuania, on 19 February 2024, 84170 Ukrainians were living in Lithuania, some of them settled in the municipality of Druskininkai. In order to reduce social exclusion, war refugees are included in the social support system. Ukrainians who have a temporary residence permit in Lithuania for humanitarian reasons can receive all child benefits (including child money and, for children in care, a foster care allowance), one-off support for settling in Lithuania, compensation for part of the housing rent, social allowances, and other social benefits, as well as general and special social services.

The state and local governments help vulnerable people through a system of social assistance that includes **cash benefits** (non-insurance benefits, benefits, compensation) and **non-monetary measures** (services, in-kind support). In the most general sense, social assistance in Lithuania is seen as a means to reduce and prevent poverty objectives. The objectives of social assistance are formulated in the Social Assistance Concept of the Lithuanian Republic. The aim is to ensure the basic living conditions and minimum needs of deprived persons/families and to reduce their social exclusion. A well-functioning social assistance system should ensure the minimum needs of the individual/family and, in the long term, empower individuals to take care of these needs independently and avoid long-term poverty traps. The system also acts as a preventive measure to minimise the number of people falling into poverty.

The focus on **poverty reduction** is very actual for the country as the latest available data shows that Lithuania's at-risk-of-poverty rates have been among the highest in the EU for many years. In 2022 the at-risk-of-poverty rate in the country was 20.9%. In 2022, the absolute poverty line was €267 per month per capita and €561 per family, consisting of two adults and two children under 14 years of age. It should be noted that the poverty risk level in Druskininkai municipality is lower than the national level and shows a downward trend. In 2017, the indicator in Druskininkai municipality was 20%, while in Lithuania it was 22.9%. In 2022, its value was 19.8%, while in Lithuania – 20.8%. Despite the downward trend, the indicator remains high in comparison with the average in the EU.

Table 5. The at-risk-of-poverty rate, percent.

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Druskininkai municipality	26.2	23.2	20.3	17.1	19.8
Lithuania	22.9	20.6	20.9	20	20.9

Source: the Ministry of Social Security and Labour of the Republic of Lithuania, 2024.

According to an annual report by the National Network of Poverty Reduction Organisations (2023), the most vulnerable to the risk of poverty in Lithuania were the unemployed, single persons, single parents with children, old-age pensioners, people with disabilities, and children. However, the main groups affected by poverty vary from region to region. According to the survey conducted by the Local Action Group, the groups most affected by social exclusion in Druskininkai municipality are the following.

Table 6. Groups most affected by social exclusion in Druskininkai municipality.

Vulnerable group	The proportion of respondents who identified this group as the most vulnerable (out of the 15 groups offered, the respondent could choose only 3)
Seniors (65 years and older) - %.	32.9
Homeless, addicts	22.7
Children, youth	22.1
People with disabilities and/or their family members	18.5
Unemployed	16,0
Single parents	14.6
Large families	13.8

Source: Druskininkai Local Action Group (2023).

5.2 Labour market

The unemployment rate in Druskininkai municipality is still higher than the corresponding indicator for Alytus County and the country.

Table 7. Unemployed as a percentage of the working-age population in 2014-2022.

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Druskininkai municipality	11,6	10,4	9,9	8,4	9,3	8,9	14,0	16,3	10,7
Alytus county	13,9	12,6	11,7	10,7	10,7	10,0	14,9	15,7	10,0
Lithuania	10,8	10,1	9,4	9,0	9,5	9,2	13,4	13,8	9,4

Source: <https://lietuvosfinansai.lt/gki/rodikliai-savivaldybese/>

The situation is expected to improve shortly as the tourism crisis linked to the COVID-19 pandemic is over. Moreover, the Employment Promotion and Motivation Services for the Unemployed and Beneficiaries of Social Assistance (known as **case management**) model has been launched in all

municipalities since 2023. The new model helps the long-term unemployed to receive comprehensive services and personalised assistance to help them return to the labour market.

Druskininkai municipality has an **unconventional distribution of unemployment rates by gender**. The share of unemployed women in the working-age population was 9.5% and correlated with the national average in 2022. The share of unemployed men in the working-age population was 12%, which was 3.3% higher than the national average of 8.7%. The trend that the share of unemployed men in the working-age population in Druskininkai municipality is higher than the national average has been observed during the whole of the last decade. This is determined by the specific features of Druskininkai municipality. The geographical location of the town and the principles of spatial development limit the development of heavy industry, big farms, and large construction projects. As a result, existing businesses and new investors are focusing on activities whose development is directly linked to the development of medical services, tourism and recreation, sports, and cultural events. Hence, it can be argued that the high unemployment rate and the higher share of unemployed men in the working-age population are due to the low number of businesses in the construction sector and heavy industry enterprises that offer jobs for most male-dominated professions.

The number of job vacancies in 2022 was 61 and the labour supply was 7.8% higher than in 2014. The **growth of the labour supply** was higher than in the Alytus region (2%), but significantly lower than the average for Lithuania, where this indicator was higher over the period from 2014 to 2022. However, companies usually offer jobs that do not require high qualifications or higher education and are poorly paid. The largest number of job vacancies was in the **tourism services sector**, which is looking to recruit chambermaids, cooks, and waiters (Lithuanian Employment Services, Job offers).

The average monthly net wage was similar to that of Alytus county, but slightly lower than that of the Republic of Lithuania. The lower wages than in the country can be explained by the predominance of the tourism-oriented services sector in Druskininkai municipality, where average wages are lower than in the financial, IT services, and manufacturing sectors.

5.3 Access to services

Social services in the territory of Druskininkai municipality are provided by the budgetary institution of non-stationary social services “Druskininkai Municipality Social Services Centre”, and **21 non-governmental organisations: 5 public institutions, 2 religious communities, 10 associations, 2 charity and support foundations, and 2 rural communities**. Social services were also provided to the residents of the municipality by several organisations registered in other municipalities (Druskininkai Municipality Strategic Development Plan 2021-2029). All organisations are equal partners of the municipality in the field of social assistance.

Despite all efforts, according to the residents, one of the most pressing social problems in Druskininkai municipality is the lack of access to social services and health care. The survey conducted by the Local Action Group showed that, although 21% of the respondents identified this issue as particularly important, a large part of the population lacks information about the social support and services they are entitled to (Druskininkai Local Action Group, 2023).

The vision of Druskininkai municipality for the development of social services for the next 3 years is to ensure that the inhabitants of the municipality receive timely, high-quality social services that are attractive, innovative, accessible and open to the public, according to their needs. During this period, the local government planned the following actions: 1) Modernisation and development of non-stationary social services in the community (especially in rural areas) for the elderly and persons with disabilities and for other social groups of the population (development of sheltered housing, independent living houses, social workshops, day centres, the establishment of preventive social services, etc.); 2) Development of remote social services; 3) Partial outsourcing of social services to NGOs; 4) Accreditation of social services, improvement of the quality of social services, improvement of the competence of the social workers, and the dissemination of information on social services for the population (Druskininkai Municipality Strategic Development Plan 2021-2029).

The main challenges of Druskininkai region and reasons behind it, also main drivers of vulnerability were discussed at the 1st research seminar with the members of the MAP of Druskininkai, which took place on 20 March, 2024, in Druskininkai. 22 experts have participated in this meeting. Questions for discussions are provided in Annex 1.

Representatives of the Druskininkai region highlighted several important socio-economic drivers in the region. The most challenging is the **lack of diversity in livelihoods**, so people do not have many options to choose between different ways of ensuring regular income and expected quality of life. Another important challenge is overall constant **changes in the global economy**. And finally, Druskininkai is suffering from the continuous **brain drain** from the region, which stands not only for today's socio-economic challenges but also for increasingly maturing problems of socioeconomic development in the future.

Considering the most important governance and security issues, the majority of interviewed representatives from different stakeholder groups pointed out the **complicated legislative basis**, which does not allow new entrepreneurs to feel safe when starting own businesses. Moreover, members of the community were unanimous that the **quality of employment services**, as well as the **quality of health services**, are low.

Next to that, it should be highlighted, that **inadequate and/or unreliable physical infrastructure** in the region's settlements leads to poorer living conditions for local people. More specifically, lack of sewage, disposal, and water supply infrastructure in Druskininkai rural areas are observed. Another challenge that is important from an overall socio-economic and environmental point of view is the overprotection of nature, which highly reduces business development opportunities in the region.

6. Assets and potentials in the region

Druskininkai municipality has the characteristics that make a region attractive in the new global environment. First, the regional economy is based on the service sector. Local businesses in Druskininkai city are strongly oriented towards tourism, and the majority of tourists can be classified as health tourists looking for treatment or wellness services. Most of them are seeking knowledge-based services that require highly professional employees and the capacities of service providers to operate tacit knowledge. In addition to the well-developed health tourism facilities, the territory of Druskininkai municipality has a **huge, under-utilised tourism potential** around the city of Druskininkai – protected natural areas, cultural heritage sites, amateur art, national heritage and crafts, and traditional events. Local agriculture is not intensive, the municipality developed environmentally friendly local transport and a high recycling rate for municipal waste. The mentioned characteristics of the region attract visitors at a slower, greener pace and encourage the development of such forms of tourism as eco-tourism, educational tourism, gastronomic tourism, and rural tourism. Druskininkai city is an international resort, so the development of dynamic cultural life and diverse travel-related services in the surroundings of the city could therefore make a significant contribution to the attractiveness of the region, raise the profile of the area, and encourage the involvement and satisfaction of visitors and local people.

In combination with national and municipal strategic management, the main strategies to handle risks and vulnerabilities are offered by the **Local Action Group (LAG)**. Druskininkai LAG has been active in the municipality since 2007, with 9 village communities and the Druskininkai Municipal Council as founders. The LAG's activities represent the interests of the rural population and include the preparation and implementation of local development strategies for the Druskininkai rural area for a period of 5 years. LAG strategies receive financial support from the EU and national funds. For example, EUR 1 142 758 was allocated for the implementation of the Local Development Strategy 2015-2020 under the LEADER instrument of the Lithuanian Rural Development Programme 2014-2020.

As the tourism sector recovers from the COVID-19 pandemic, tourist flows generate substantial income and employ both highly skilled and unskilled labour. It has a positive impact on social well-being. Investing in new forms of tourism brings long-term multiple benefits: it strengthens the identity of society, builds a sustainable state, promotes economic growth, and international competitiveness. In the opinion of Druskininkai LAG, it is essential to intensify the support for the development of tourism services with special attention to the hidden tourism potential of rural areas. The social initiatives of local organisations and businesses can complement urban tourist attractions, enabling visitors to experience a different Druskininkai. They would strengthen the local economy and contribute to solving social problems.

The potential of the region's development is also characterised by the capacity of the local population to attract **EU and other funds** to the area. According to the EU support portal www.esinvesticijos.lt, Druskininkai has been very successful in racing EU funds. Druskininkai municipality has been allocated €105.7 million of EU funding for the period 2014-2022. In terms of EU funds per capita, Druskininkai

municipality attracted €5,278 per capita between 2014 and 2022, compared to €1,269 per capita in Alytus county and €163 per capita in the Republic of Lithuania.

A large part of EU funding goes on developing the social economy. According to the last surveys (Druskininkai local action group, 2023), the perspective for social business in the territory of the Druskininkai municipality is very positive – local communities and NGO organisations have expressed a clear need for the establishment and development of such businesses. Moreover, the local government has a positive attitude towards social entrepreneurship as a tool for the regeneration of the region. The integration of NGOs and rural community-based organisations into the network of social service providers is one of its main objectives in the short term. 2 village communities are already included in the network of social service providers (Druskininkai Municipality Social Services Plan 2023). In 2022, municipal spending on social services provided by NGOs compared to total municipal spending on social services amounted to 12%.

The growing so-called **sharing (or gig) economy** with the platform-based organization of work opens new possibilities for the development of social businesses. Individuals can give outsiders access to underused resources, assets, or services (paid or unpaid) via digital platforms or analogue forums. Platforms can be various; they can offer household services; accommodation and facilities; professional services; peer-to-peer transport, car-sharing; collaborative finance; etc. The platform-based economy creates new sources of income and changes labour market structure. At the same time, the challenges to reorganize the social security system arise paying particular attention to the motivations for entering platform work, the conditions of platform work and the extent of social protection afforded platform workers (Adams et. al., 2018; Cherry & Aloisi, 2016; Cunningham-Parmeter, 2016; Davis & Sinha, 2021; Joice et al., 2019; Prassl & Risak, 2016; Todoli Signes, 2017). The main challenge is to identify new vulnerability factors and find ways to reduce their impact taking into account local specificities.

According to the research of the Local Action Group, the most inspiration for raising new collaborative projects comes after seeing good examples (Druskininkai local action group, 2023). For instance, a promising practice of an innovative platform-based social business model is demonstrated by the organization *Sūrūs vėjai* (*in English: Salty Winds*), a public enterprise that aims to educate the public through a custom-tailored piece of entertainment. The organisation acts as a platform offering educational programmes to businesses or tourist groups, and thus enabling local people (farmers, craftsmen, artists, rural communities in Druskininkai municipality) to provide their services, sell their products, and promote local culture and crafts. In order to offer a variety of services to tourists, the platform cooperates with tourist attractions, spa centres, and other organisations operating in Druskininkai Resort.

In summary, the strengths of the Druskininkai Municipality can be described as follows:

- **innovative social businesses** oriented to the global environment,
- **growing NGO sector, active village communities** able to attract investment from various funds and implement projects necessary for local development,

- growing number of active **self-employed** population,
- **increasing population** caused by migration due to the attractiveness of living near Druskininkai city.

7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP

According to the Social Assistance Effectiveness Index, the situation in Druskininkai municipality is better than average in Lithuania. However, the Index shows a picture that mainly deals with social vulnerability because of poverty. As argued by the last insights in the theory of social assistance, the reduction of poverty does not cover all vulnerabilities. For example, Leisering (2018, p. 335) points out that „ social assistance is ‘fundamental but not comprehensive’, i.e. the challenge of universalizing social citizenship extends beyond relieving poverty. To confront the problem of inequality and get the middle classes on board, cash transfers need to be embedded in a broader, multi-tiered architecture of social security, which increases political support also for cash transfers.

At the same time, it is important to note that **vulnerabilities change over time and are context specific**. According to the mental model of the industrial era, from the perspective of individuals or particular population groups, regions are attractive because they are economically successful and/or because they offer a good quality of life (Russo & Smith, 2012). The social risks of the industrial era have been analysed and considered in most countries. To counteract the main risk factors, many policy tools have been developed to ensure a stable and organised distribution and redistribution of social opportunities and social protection: the labour market, the family and the welfare state (Ranci, et al. 2010). In the post-industrial era, based on the service economy, new social risks have emerged. Social vulnerability has become a complex phenomenon and should be considered a multi-dimensional phenomenon affecting contemporary post-industrial societies of Western Europe due to the emergence of new social risks in the past two decades. According to Ranci et al. (2010), they are the following: flexibilization of the labour market, polarization in the housing market, and the consequent increase in housing deprivation, income insecurity and the spread of dependency as a consequence of the aging of the population. These new social risks have contributed to a weakening of the *coordination* among the three fundamental mechanisms of social inclusion that in Keynesian societies ensured the stable and organized distribution and redistribution of social opportunities and social protection: the labour market, the family, and the welfare state. As a consequence, in the past decade, uncertainty and insecurity have spread across the continent more than before. Thus, regenerative regional development strategies should respond to new development challenges and opportunities, oriented toward cardinal changes in economic relations and the new global environment.

As pointed out by Navickè (2023, p. 92), “Contemporary Lithuania can be attributed to a post-Fordist life course regime, which is characterised by de-standardisation and de-politicisation of the life course, and transformation of social policy institutions towards more flexibility to accommodate and facilitate this change.” Hence, the national and regional strategies should be oriented to creating a post-industrial society according to the rules of the collaborative service economy. The key challenges to Druskininkai municipality are developing a collaborative platform-based service economy and more effectively attracting specific target groups (green business investors, talent, and visitors) that are important for the development of the region in the new global environment.

The development and dissemination of Salty Winds' innovative, social business model, based on the latest developments in the theory of business model innovation, could become a pilot project which emphasizes two paradigm innovations of the post-industrial era: 1) platform-based business model and 2) servitization of farming and crafts. Both innovations are very poorly researched in the contexts of social inclusion and social economy.

8. Annex 1. Questionnaire of main drivers of rural vulnerability

The data will be used for research purposes only, in aggregated manner and anonymously. The research is carried out by researchers from the Lithuanian Social Science Centre, Institute of Economics and Rural Development.

The concept of vulnerability encompasses various interpretations and perspectives. In your opinion, what are the main factors shaping the social vulnerability of the population of Druskininkai municipality that should be focused on in the near future?

I. Socio-economic factors (choose three, ranking them from the most important - 1 to the least important - 2 and 3):

- (a) Lack of diversity of livelihoods
- b) Illegal economic activities
- c) Arbitrariness of employers
- d) Lack of access to new information
- e) Local people who are unable to pay because of poverty
- f) Unattractive for new investors
- g) Brain drain from the region
- h) Unstable national economy
- i) Constant changes in the global economy
- j) Lack of health services for a certain population group (please specify)
- k) Lack of social protection measures for a certain population group (please specify)
- l) Insert your own:

II. Governance and security factors (choose three, ranking them from most important - 1 - to least important - 2 and 3):

- (a) Lack of opportunities to participate in regional governance decisions
- b) The legal framework does not allow to feel secure in starting one's own business
- c) Low quality of employment services
- d) Unreasonable decisions by the labour inspectorate
- e) Poorly organised and/or poorly monitored legal framework for agricultural workers/farmers
- f) Abuse of criminal power by local authorities

- g) Abuse of access to the region's natural resources by the authorities
 - h) Low quality health services
 - i) Poor services of local educational institutions
 - j) Violent conflicts in workplaces
 - k) Domestic violence with impunity
 - l) Sexual harassment at work
 - m) Prevalent discriminatory practices against certain groups of the population (please specify which)
.....
 - n) Please add your own:
- III. Environmental factors (choose three, ranked from most important - 1 - to least important - 2 and 3):
- (a) Inadequate or unreliable physical infrastructure in settlements leads to poorer living conditions for the local population
 - b) Climate change makes farming more difficult
 - c) Technologies used by local enterprises pollute the environment
 - d) Overprotection of nature reduces business development opportunities
 - e) Residents of Druskininkai municipality feel they live in a remote location
 - f) Please write your own:

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10. Partners

